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Abstract:

This deliverable describes the first release of the SSHOC Training Toolkit launched in April 2020. The Toolkit consists of an inventory of various learning and training materials that trainers in the Social Sciences and Humanities can use to develop and improve their own training activities. The Toolkit will be further developed in collaboration with the SSHOC Training Community and presented and evaluated during the SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps.

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Contributor List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
DANS	Ricarda Braukmann	ricarda.braukmann@dans.knaw.nl
DANS	Ellen Leenarts	ellen.leenarts@dans.knaw.nl
LIBER	Tatsiana Yankelevich	Tatsiana.Yankelevich@KB.nl
LIBER	Vasso Kalaitzi	Vasso.Kalaitzi@KB.nl
LIBER	Martina Torma	Martina.Torma@KB.nl
LIBER	Friedel Grant	Friedel.Grant@KB.nl
DARIAH/OEAW	Matej Durco	Matej.Durco@oeaw.ac.at
DARIAH/OEAW	Klaus Illmayer	Klaus.Illmayer@oeaw.ac.at
TRUST-IT	Leonardo Marino	l.marino@trust-it-services.com
TRUST_IT	Marieke Willems	m.willems@trust-it-services.com
CLARIN	Jakob Lenardic	jakob.lenardic@ff.uni-lj.si
CLARIN	Darja Fiser	darja.fiser@ff.uni-lj.si
CLARIN	Kristina Pahor de Maiti	Kristina.PahordeMaiti@ff.uni-lj.si
CESSDA/UKDA	Veerle Van Den Eynden,	veerle@essex.ac.uk
UCL	Alejandra Albuérne	a.albuérne@ucl.ac.uk
GESIS	Ann-Kathrin Reinl	Ann-Kathrin.Reinl@gesis.org

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the first release of the SSHOC Training Toolkit which was launched on April 20th 2020¹. The Toolkit consists of an inventory of various learning and training materials that trainers in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) can use to develop and improve their own training activities.

The Toolkit at the time of the launch listed over 70 materials from 41 different sources in various formats, such as slides, modules, videos, games and other items. Materials cover a range of topics including Research Data Management, FAIR data, text encoding, Open Science, and quantitative analysis, as well as didactics for better development and implementation of training activities

Information about these train-the-trainer materials was collected and are displayed using a dedicated drupal-based application that was already utilized for the inventory of existing training materials described in *D6.7 Inventory of existing learning materials* (Đurčo, Illmayer & Barbot, 2019).

The Toolkit will be further developed in collaboration with the SSHOC Training Community and presented and evaluated during the SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps.

Note on the terminology

While the original title of the toolkit mentioned in the grant proposal and agreement was “SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Toolkit” rather than “SSHOC Training Toolkit”, the task team has decided to adapt the name to “SSHOC Training Toolkit” as it more accurately describes the content of the toolkit and its use. The Toolkit is directed at SSH trainers, but next to train-the-trainer materials, the toolkit also contains information on other learning and training materials available for the SSH community. The development of the toolkit was based on an already performed inventory for SSH learning materials (D6.7) and it was felt that the collected information was of use to SSH trainers and the SSH community as well. Therefore, it was decided to adjust the name of the toolkit to better reflect its content and potential use. The term “SSHOC Training Toolkit” is hence used in the deliverable names and in the SSHOC online communication.

¹ The SSHOC Training Toolkit can be accessed at <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/> [accessed on 29th of April 2020]

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CESSDA	Consortium of Social Science Data Archives
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IASSIST	International Association for Social Science Information Services and Technology
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

Task 6.4 of SSHOC Work Package 6 concerns the building of expertise within the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) training community. One of the key outcomes of this task and a milestone in the project (MS40) is the development of a SSHOC Training Toolkit. The Toolkit is meant to serve as a framework for training design, organisation and delivery and is developed to aid trainers in the Social Sciences and Humanities by providing them with materials that they can utilize in their own training activities. While there are many organisations that offer educational materials for trainers in the SSH, it is often difficult to find these materials. Therefore, the SSHOC Training Toolkit was developed to provide a curated inventory of train-the-trainer materials on relevant topics that SSH trainers can find, access and reuse. The Toolkit brings together information about the train-the-trainer materials developed and provided by the different SSHOC partners, other relevant training nodes that the project has identified, as well as other sources. Materials developed over the course of the project will also be available in the Toolkit.

The SSHOC Training Community, described in more detail in the Deliverable *D6.10 Report on the SSHOC Training Community*, is the main target audience for the SSHOC Training Toolkit. Therefore, its members also play an important role in the collection of feedback on the first iteration of the Toolkit described in this deliverable. In addition to actively using the Toolkit, the Training Community will also be asked to contribute materials and thereby co-create the final version of the SSHOC Training Toolkit that will be released later in the project and described in Deliverable *D6.11 SSHOC Training Toolkit (final)*.

This deliverable describes the development and release of the first iteration of the SSHOC Training Toolkit. It is an online inventory in which information is collected about a range of learning and training materials available to SSH trainers from various sources, including SSHOC partners as well as identified training nodes. Training nodes are organisations that foster coordinated and cross-disciplinary training across the SSH domains. The identified nodes for SSHOC include for instance, EOSC-Hub, Parthenos or OpenAIRE, as well as SSHOC partners like CESSDA or DARIAH. The SSHOC training nodes are described in more detail in *Deliverable 6.10 - Report on the SSHOC Training Community*. The Toolkit also contains materials from a range of topics including Research Data Management, FAIR data, Open Science, as well as materials on training development and didactics. Trainers can find various types of materials, including, for instance, modules, workshops, slides, videos, exercises and games. Importantly, the toolkit covers materials which are relevant across disciplines, for instance educational materials on Research Data Management or FAIR data, as well as materials specifically designed for the SSH community and their training needs.

The first iteration of the SSHOC Training Toolkit has been based on an inventory developed in WP6 Task 6.3 to collect information on existing learning materials in the field of SSH. This inventory was extended with materials specifically directed at trainers to serve as the SSHOC Training Toolkit. A drupal-based application was used to collect and curate the materials which allows for the extraction of the collected information into other formats and services that may be developed in the future.

In the following section, the development of the Toolkit is described in more detail, explaining the sources that were consulted (section 2.1) as well as the application that was used (section 2.2). Section 3 of this deliverable provides an overview of the materials available in the first iteration of the SSHOC Training Toolkit as well as its functionalities. Finally, the last section of this deliverable describes the future plans for the Toolkit and its final iteration.

2. Development of the Training Toolkit

2.1 Identification of sources

The development of the Training Toolkit built upon the work conducted for Deliverable *D6.7 Inventory of Existing Learning Materials* (Đurčo, Illmayer, & Barbot, 2019). In this deliverable, a number of sources that provide SSH learning materials for a variety of audiences (including researchers, data creators or students) were identified. These sources included SSHOC partners such as CESSDA, DARIAH or CLARIN, as well as other sources, including for instance EOSC-Hub and OpenAIRE.

The term *source* as used in the Toolkit and in this deliverable refers to an organisation, group or project that provides learning or training materials. The individual learning or training materials that are provided by the organisation, group or project are called *items* in the Toolkit and in this deliverable.

For the SSHOC Training Toolkit, the sources already identified in D6.7 were evaluated. From the 35 sources that D6.7 had identified, 18 sources also provide train-the-trainer materials and these sources were hence included in the curation process for the Training Toolkit. In addition, Task 6.4 identified 23 additional sources relevant for SSH trainers, resulting in a total of 41 sources with train-the-trainer materials available in the first iteration of the Training Toolkit. An overview of the sources identified from T6.7 as well as the additional sources is given in Table 1. All sources and the number of items per source are shown in Appendix 1.

Table 1. Overview of the sources providing train-the-trainer materials included in the Training Toolkit. A number of sources were taken from a list of sources identified in D6.7 and additional sources were added.

Sources - identified in D6.7	Sources - additional
CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide	Alison
CLARIN Knowledge Sharing	CLARIN Depositing Services
DARIAH Campus	CLARIN Legal Information Platform
Data Carpentry	CLARIN Resource Families
European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (EHRI)	Coursera
FOSTER Open Sciences: Courses	DANS

Harvard University: online courses	Data Observation Network for Earth (DataOne)
Journal of Open Source Education	DCAF
Library Carpentry	Digital Curation Centre
OpenAIRE	European Commission Open Access & Data Management
PARTHENOS: Training Suite	FD Mentor
SERISS: Training Overview	GESIS Notebooks
Software Carpentry	GESIS Training
TeSS (Training eSupport System)	INASP
The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE): Special Data Sets	JISC
Training material EOSC Hub	LFT
UK Data Service: Manage Data web resource	New Mexico Broadband Program
Research Data Mantra	NHS Education for Scotland
	OpenScience MOOC
	RDNL/DCC/University of Edinburgh
	Research Data Netherlands RDNL
	TU Delft - DelftX
	UNODC

2.2 Description of sources and items

Following the identification of sources, each source was assigned a curator, i.e. one of the partners involved in Task 6.4, who was responsible for describing the source and, where relevant, adding and describing specific items for the sources which were considered to be of particular interest for the SSH trainer community. A similar approach as described in D6.7 was followed and a small number of items for a selection of sources was described to provide an indication of the available train-the-trainer materials. This resulted in 76 items relevant for trainers in the first iteration of the Training Toolkit (see Appendix 1). The train-the-trainer content displayed in the Training Toolkit is therefore not meant to be exhaustive but rather gives an impression of the variety of materials that are available.

2.3 Application

The Training Toolkit that is accessible at <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/> is built on a drupal-based application that was also used in the collection of learning materials described in D6.7. A similar curation

strategy was used to collect and curate materials relevant for trainers, and the data model that is used in the Training Toolkit is the same as the model described in D6.7 (see Figure 1). A number of closed vocabularies as well as open fields were used to describe the sources and items.

Figure 1. Data model for sources and items in the drupal-based application

For each of the identified sources (see Table 1), a number of elements could be described by the curators, including the intended audience, relevant discipline, topics covered, extent, status etc. Additionally, for selected sources, individual items were selected from the available train-the-trainer materials and these items were described in further detail. The closed vocabularies and open fields that were used for these descriptions are listed in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively. Closed vocabularies contained a set of terms the curators could select, whereas open fields were free-text fields that curators could use to describe the sources and items.

Table 2. Closed vocabularies used to describe the sources and items

Closed vocabularies	Description
Curated topics	A list of terms selected from the full list of topics which curators described for the sources and items.
Formats	Types of training materials, like webinar, e-learning module, blog-entry, games, etc.
Audiences	The kind of scholars the material is intended for. For the Training Toolkit the audience are trainers, and in some cases also data stewards.
Statuses	Tentative indication of the stage in the lifecycle of a source, i.e. is it a prototype still in development, or rather a legacy resource that is in danger to disappear.

Table 3. Open fields used to describe the sources and items

Open fields	Description
Disciplines	Scholarly disciplines for which given material primarily applies, mostly taken as indicated by the sources.
Languages	Language of the content of the material.
Licenses	License formulating the conditions of (re-)use of the material, e.g. Creative Commons Attribution. Ideally this should be an unambiguous reference (URL) to a license definition
Organisations	Legal entities responsible for providing (maintaining and curating) a given source.
Topics	Keywords describing what a training material is about. As opposed to “curated topics”, this field is meant to collect keywords in an open manner as they are applied in the individual sources and items.

The closed vocabularies and open fields were largely based on the work done in Task 6.3. However, the closed vocabularies were extended where necessary to include relevant terms for train-the-trainer materials that were not yet covered in the originally defined closed vocabularies. For instance, the element *Game* was added to the vocabulary *Formats* as several sources offered games that trainers can use in their educational activities. A *Curated topic* that is highly relevant for trainers but was not yet covered in the curated topics identified in D6.7

was *Didactics*. Curated topics available in the first iteration of the Training Toolkit include the following 14 elements:

- Citizen science
- Copyright
- Data visualization
- Didactics
- Digital edition
- Git [a distributed version-control system for tracking changes in source code during software development]
- Open Science
- Programming with R
- Python/Jupyter
- Quantitative analysis
- Research data management/FAIR data
- Spatial data
- Survey data
- Text encoding and TEI

Formats of materials available in the first iteration of the Training Toolkit include the following 15 elements

- Blog
- Book
- Checklist
- Course
- Data Notebook (jupyter)
- E-learning module
- Events
- Game
- Items
- Report
- Slides
- Unit/Lesson
- Video
- Webinar
- Workshop

It should be noted that the vocabularies and fields used in this first iteration of the Training Toolkit will be evaluated and extended. If needed they will be changed over the course of the SSHOC project to better fit the content of the Toolkit and to align with terms and vocabularies used in other services. As new sources and items will be added, the need for more curated topics or different fields to describe the data may arise. In

addition, the application that is currently used to display the Toolkit may also change according to the developments made in the SSHOC marketplace. As described in section 4 of this deliverable, the Toolkit will be evaluated in collaboration with the SSHOC Training Community and this initial work will be adapted to provide a Toolkit that suits the needs of the community in an optimal fashion.

3. First iteration of the Training Toolkit

The first iteration of the Training Toolkit was released on April 20th 2020 and is available at <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/>.

The SSHOC Training toolkit provides an inventory of SSH training materials. More information can be found on the [SSHOC Training website](#).

Search entities

Displaying 1 - 117 of 117

ID	Title	Description	Curated topics
232	Alison	Alison is one of the world's largest free learning platforms for education and skills training.	Didactics
43	CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide	The Data Management Expert Guide is designed by European experts from the CESSDA Training Working Group to	Didactics , Research data management/FAIR data

Entity type

- Item (76)
- Source (41)

Collections

- Training Toolkit (117)

Figure 2. Screenshot of the main page of the toolkit

The main page of the Training Toolkit lists all the sources in the Toolkit followed by all the available items. On the right-hand side the user has the option to select the intended audience and filter sources or items based on language, curated topics, topic, discipline and format (see Table 2 and 3). The user also has the option to search the Toolkit with a free text search field located at the top of the page.

When the user selects a given source, they can view the source description and all the metadata that has been provided by the curators as shown in the example in Figure 3. On the right-hand side, the user can find the link to the external access point of the source. In addition, sources and items that focus on the audience trainers have received a special collection tag "Training Toolkit", which is as well visible in the box on the right-hand side. This tag was added to distinguish the items and sources relevant for trainers that were added in the work conducted for this deliverable from the sources and items that were curated for D6.7 (i.e. training and learning materials for other audiences).

CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide

Source

The Data Management Expert Guide is designed by European experts from the CESSDA [Training Working Group](#) to help social science researchers make their research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR).

The guide is written for social science researchers who are in an early stage of practising research data management. With this guide, CESSDA wants to contribute to professionalism in data management and increase the value of research data.

The guide leads through the research data lifecycle from planning, organising, documenting, processing, storing and protecting data to sharing and publishing them. Taking the whole roundtrip will take approximately 15 hours.

Particular specialties of the guide is a focus on European diversity (for example in data protection legislation, research ethics, research funder DMP requirements, etc), developing a Data Management Plan as you progress through the guide, and topical expert tips.

Responsible organisation
[CESSDA](#)

Contact
CESSDA Training Group
training@cessda.eu

Created: 2018-01-01

Last updated: 2019-12-01

Harvesting
No endpoint visible or other ways to harvest. Content is very mixed: references and videos are part of it, could be complicated to harvest.

Access points
<https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Library/Data-Management-Exper...>

Collections
Training Toolkit

Items

Choose collection: Training Toolkit Apply

Title	Description	Collections
Train-the-Trainers package	<p>This Train-the-Trainers (TTT) package forms an addition to the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide which was developed by the CESSDA Training Working Group in 2017 and 2018.</p> <p>This package contains different materials that trainers can use in developing and giving Research Data Management and Discovery trainings for (social science) researchers.</p> <p>Materials for instance include workshop outlines, slides and exercises that can be reused and adapted by local RDM trainers. The package contains five different types of materials: Workshop Outlines, Exercises, Presentations, Documents and Handouts, and Images. A full overview of all materials in this TTT Package is giving below.</p>	Training Toolkit

Figure 3. Screenshot of a source page of the Training Toolkit. Example is the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide. The upper image shows the start of the page, whereas the lower image shows the bottom of the page where users can find an overview of the related items for a given source.

At the bottom of a source page (lower image Figure 3), all the items belonging to that source are listed. The user can select to view only the items belonging to the Training Toolkit collection or view all items that were curated for a given source, i.e. training and learning materials that were curated for D6.7, directed at other audiences than trainers and data stewards.

Items are presented in a similar way as the sources, but in addition to the access point and the collection, the information on the right-hand side also includes the source to which a certain item belongs. An example of an item in the Training Toolkit is given in Figure 4.

Train-the-Trainers package

Item

This Train-the-Trainers (TTT) package forms an addition to the CEESDA Data Management Expert Guide which was developed by the CEESDA Training Working Group in 2017 and 2018.

This package contains different materials that trainers can use in developing and giving Research Data Management and Discovery trainings for (social science) researchers.

Materials for instance include workshop outlines, slides and exercises that can be reused and adapted by local RDM trainers. The package contains five different types of materials: Workshop Outlines, Exercises, Presentations, Documents and Handouts, and Images. A full overview of all materials in this TTT Package is giving below.

Format
E-learning module

Language
English

License: [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Intended audience
Trainer

Access point
<https://www.ceeda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Library/Training-Packages/Tra...>

Source of item
[CEESDA Data Management Expert Guide](#)

Collections
Training Toolkit

Figure 4. Screenshot from an item page of the Training Toolkit. Example is the Train-the-trainer package from the CEESDA Data Management Expert Guide.

3.1 Content Overview

This section provides an overview of the types of materials that users can find in the first iteration of the Training Toolkit. In particular, this section describes the content in terms of their identified language, curated topic, discipline and format. It should be noted that one source or item in the Training Toolkit can have multiple languages, topics, disciplines and formats. *Language* and *Discipline* were open fields while *Curated topics* and *Formats* were closed vocabularies where curators could choose terms from a predefined list (see section 2.3, table 2 and 3). The Training Toolkit collection at the time of launch consisted of 41 sources and 76 items.

3.1.1 Language

By far, most of the materials in the Training Toolkit are available in English. However, the Training Toolkit also covers a few materials in other languages. In particular, CLARIN Depositing Services provides items in 14 different languages including for instance, French, Italian, Portuguese and Serbian. Moreover, there are two sources and six items in German, one source and two items in Dutch, one source and one item in Spanish, and one source in Arabic listed in the Training Toolkit.

3.1.2 Curated topic

Figure 5 gives an overview of the distribution of curated topics of all materials (sources and items combined) in the Training Toolkit. By far, most of the materials are related to Research Data Management and FAIR data.

The Toolkit further covers many materials on Text Encoding and TEI as well. These are mostly from CLARIN Depositing Services, CLARIN Knowledge Sharing, CLARIN Resource Families, DARIAH-CAMPUS. The Training Toolkit further covers topics like Open Science, Quantitative analysis and Didactics. Materials on didactics are of particular interest for trainers and the Toolkit currently provides 9 sources and 1 item on this topic.

Figure 5. Pie-chart displaying the number of materials (sources and items combined) in the Training Toolkit from a particular curated topic.

3.1.3 Discipline

The element discipline was used as an open field and 30 different terms were entered by the curators. Many materials in the Training Toolkit were labelled to relate to *all disciplines*. This is due to the fact that many materials cover generic topics such as Research Data Management and Open Science which relate to multiple disciplines. Besides content labelled relevant for all disciplines, the disciplines most often labelled by the curators are *Social Sciences* (19), followed by *Computational Linguistics* (14), *Corpus Linguistics* (14) and *Digital humanities* (13).

3.1.4 Formats

Figure 6 gives an overview of the distribution of formats of materials (sources and items combined) in the Training Toolkit. Most of the materials were considered to be of the format *items*, followed by *e-learning modules* and *courses*. The Toolkit also contains a number of *videos* and several *games* that trainers can use in their training activities.

Figure 6. Pie-chart displaying the number of materials (sources and items combined) in the Training Toolkit from a particular format.

4. Future Plans

This deliverable describes the first iteration of the SSHOC Training Toolkit. The Toolkit will be evaluated and extended and will change over the course of the SSHOC project.

The main target audience for the Toolkit is the SSHOC Training Community and they will also play an important part in the revision of the Toolkit. Dedicated calls for the SSHOC Training Community will be organized to present the Toolkit and ask for feedback and input.

In particular, the members of the SSHOC Training community will be encouraged to propose additional train-the-trainer materials that can be added to the Toolkit. Moreover, once trainers start using the Toolkit, feedback on the usability of the Toolkit will be collected so that gaps can be identified and the need for additional materials can be evaluated.

The open fields and closed vocabularies described above will likely need to be adjusted and extended, as new materials for the Toolkit will be gathered and feedback from the users will be received. In addition, the application that is currently used to display the Toolkit may also change according to the developments made in the SSHOC marketplace. SSHOC aims to create the Toolkit in such a way that the collected information can be integrated into other services, for instance other inventories developed in the EOSC. To this end, the Toolkit is currently based on an application that allows for the extraction of the collected metadata. Once other services mature, the current fields and vocabularies used will be evaluated and adjusted to facilitate the integration with other services and initiatives in the EOSC landscape. In this process, it will also further be investigated how the Toolkit can be used and sustained after the lifetime of the SSHOC project. The aim is to create a final version of the Toolkit that is integrated into the EOSC services for the SSH community and will be maintained within the EOSC infrastructure. The final version of the Toolkit will be released later in the project and will be described in *Deliverable D6.11 SSHOC Training Toolkit (final)*.

The next section describes the plans for collection of feedback from the SSHOC Training Community (4.1) and the SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps (4.2).

4.1 Feedback from the SSHOC Training Community

Establishing the SSHOC Training Community is one of the key deliverables of SSHOC *Work Package 6 - Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise*. It is an important contribution to the EOSC vision to build digital and Open Science skills through a coordinated, pan-European training infrastructure. The SSHOC Training Community was launched in September 2019² and the current composition as well as performed and planned activities are described in more detail in the deliverable *D6.10 Report on the SSHOC Training network* which is written simultaneously with this deliverable. The goal of establishing a SSHOC

² News item on the SSHOC Training Community launch <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/launch-sshoc-training-community-0> [accessed on 29th of April 2020]

Training Community is to build expertise while at the same time making the best possible use of resources which already exist within the SSHOC partner network. The SSHOC Training Community is the main target audience of the SSHOC Training Toolkit. Therefore, its members also play an important role in the collection of feedback on the first iteration of the Toolkit. The Community will be engaged in multiple ways. The Toolkit launch was communicated with the Training Community through a dedicated discussion e-mail list. Members are encouraged to discover the Toolkit, use materials and also promote its use in their respective communities. The Toolkit will be presented in more details during dedicated online events for the Training Community where SSHOC will showcase the Toolkit and collect feedback and input. Feedback will be gathered on the current content and the usability of the Toolkit, and stories from the Training Community on how members may have used sources and materials in their own training events will be collected. In addition to actively using the Toolkit, the Training Community will also be asked to contribute materials and thereby co-create the final version of the SSHOC Training Toolkit that will be released later in the project and described in *Deliverable D6.11 SSHOC Training Toolkit (final)*. The SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps, described in the following section will also be an important way of promoting and developing the Toolkit together with the SSHOC Training Community.

4.2 SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps

SSHOC will organize three Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps targeting SSH trainers from the SSHOC Training Community and beyond. These Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps will be used to present and collect feedback on the SSHOC Training Toolkit, as well as to help trainers use the Toolkit to develop and improve their own training skills and activities.

Two of the three bootcamps were planned in 2020 and accepted to take place along two major conferences. The first bootcamp was planned at the IASSIST conference in Sweden³ in May 2020, targeting social science scholars and the data archive community. The second bootcamp was planned at the LIBER conference in Serbia⁴ in June 2020, targeting librarians and including a hands-on session using CLARIN training materials. Due to the COVID19-crisis, these events will not take place as planned, IASSIST has been postponed to 2021 and the LIBER conference will be taking place as an online event. SSHOC is currently working on a mitigation plan for the planned bootcamps to address the new situation and still build and empower the SSHOC Training Community and receive feedback on the Toolkit. For this purpose, elements of the bootcamps will be taken online during the COVID19-crisis and feedback on the Training Toolkit will be collected in this way. Face-to-face bootcamps will be organized later in 2020, if possible, and in 2021 once the COVID19-crisis has been defeated.

³ Link to the IASSIST conference: <https://iassist2020.org/> [accessed on 29th of April 2020]

⁴ Link to the LIBER conference <https://libereurope.eu/events/liber-2020-annual-conference/> [accessed on 29th of April 2020]

5. Conclusion

This deliverable describes the first iteration of the SSHOC Training Toolkit that was released on 20th of April 2020. It is meant for trainers in the Social Sciences and Humanities and provides an inventory of learning and training materials that scholars can use in their own training activities. The current Toolkit contains 76 items from 41 sources covering a variety of topics and material types. The Toolkit will be further developed in collaboration with members of the SSHOC Training Community who will provide feedback and input for the following iterations that will be developed throughout the SSHOC project. The final version of the Toolkit will be released later in the project and will be described in Deliverable *D6.11 SSHOC Training Toolkit (final)*.

6. Appendix - Overview of sources and items available through the SSHOC Training Toolkit

Sources of the Training Toolkit	Items
Alison	0
CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide	1
CLARIN Depositing Services	13
CLARIN Knowledge Sharing	0
CLARIN Legal Information Platform	3
CLARIN Resource Families	17
Coursera	1
DANS	1
DARIAH Campus	3
Data Carpentry	0
Data Observation Network for Earth (DataOne)	1
DCAF	0
Digital Curation Centre	2
European Commission Open access & Data management	1
European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (EHRI)	1
FD Mentor	1
FOSTER Open Sciences: Courses	6
GESIS Notebooks	2
GESIS Training	3
Harvard University: online courses	1
INASP	0
JISC	1
Journal of Open Source Education	0

LFT	0
Library Carpentry	0
New Mexico Broadband Program	0
NHS Education for Scotland	0
OpenAIRE	2
OpenScience MOOC	2
PARTHENOS: Training Suite	3
RDNL/DCC/University of Edinburgh	0
Research Data MANTRA	2
Research Data Netherlands RDNL	1
SERISS: Training overview	0
Software Carpentry	0
TeSS (Training eSupport System)	2
The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE): Special Data Sets	1
Training material EOSC Hub	1
TU Delft - DelftX	1
UK Data Service: Manage Data	5
UNODC	0
Total items of all 41 sources	76

7. References

Đurčo, M., Illmayer, K., & Barbot, L. (2019). SSHOC D6.7 Inventory of existing learning materials (Version v1.0). *Zenodo*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3596002>

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